

Vietnamese EFL University Students' Perceptions and Experiences of Using the ELSA Speak Application for Developing English Oral Fluency

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ABSTRACT

This case study examines Vietnamese EFL university students' perceptions and experiences with using the ELSA Speak application to enhance their English oral fluency. Over a four-week period, seven participants engaged with the app, having data collected through screen recordings, daily reflective diaries and semi-structured interviews. Thematic analysis revealed that learners valued a combination of authentic interaction, structured repetition and explicit feedback. Features that supported personalisation, motivation, and future goals, such as 'Study by Topic', 'Improve Pronunciation', 'ELSA AI Conversation', 'Practice Daily Lessons', and 'Earn a Certificate', were especially valued. However, technical limitations, content lacking depth of expertise and inadequate tracking features emerged as sources of frustration that could impede sustained engagement.

Keywords: AI-assisted language learning, artificial intelligence (AI), ELSA Speak, mobile-assisted language learning, skill acquisition theory

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INTRODUCTION

As English has become a crucial means of international communication, proficiency in spoken English has been a significant goal for many learners, particularly in countries where English is considered a foreign language (Kirkpatrick, 2010). Among all the speaking skills, the quest for oral fluency in the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) setting has gained increasing significance, especially within the context of globalisation. However, despite years of classroom instruction, many EFL students may be able to produce grammatically correct sentences on paper but struggle to speak fluently and confidently (Farrokhi & Mahmoudi, 2014).

In Vietnam, developing learners' English-speaking proficiency is often neglected in test-oriented education (Thao & Xuan, 2020). Many high school graduates are fearful of making mistakes and not confident in speaking English (Van Tuyen & Loan, 2019). In 2016, the Ministry of Education and Training reported that the National Foreign Languages Project 2020, which received nearly 500 million dollars in funding to improve the country's English education, had not met its targets, and the failure was due mainly to unrealistic benchmarks and insufficient instructional time (Tran & Tanemura, 2020).

In response to these challenges, Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) has emerged as a promising alternative. The rapid growth of smartphones and mobile applications has transformed the way learners access language resources. Among the range of mobile applications available, those powered by generative Artificial Intelligence (AI)—such as ELSA Speak—have gained notable attention. Evers and Chen (2020) noted that these apps employ advanced speech recognition technologies to provide instant feedback on pronunciation, fluency and intonation and offer learners a sense of autonomy and control over their language learning.

Despite the growing popularity of ELSA Speak (Kaiser, 2024), limited research has examined in-depth learners' experiences with the app, particularly in the Vietnamese EFL context. Most existing studies are experimental, focusing on quantitative outcomes such as test scores or pronunciation accuracy, whereas few have explored how learners perceive, interact with, and evaluate the app (discussed further below). Meanwhile, understanding these user experiences is vital for evaluating the app's pedagogical values, identifying its strengths and limitations, and informing future design and implementation. Therefore, the current study aims to address this gap by examining Vietnamese EFL university

students' perceptions and experiences with ELSA Speak for the development of their oral fluency.

REVIEW OF PREVIOUS RESEARCH

This section reviews previous studies on Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL), focusing on its application in oral fluency development in EFL contexts and learners' perceptions of using mobile applications in their language learning.

MALL and oral fluency in EFL contexts

MALL involves the use of mobile devices to support second or foreign language learning. In fact, Melhuish and Falloon (2010) highlight five defining features of MALL—portability, ubiquity, situated learning, connectivity, and personalisation—which allow learners to access language input beyond the classroom. Recent years have seen significant advances in integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into MALL, particularly in speaking practice and assessment (Zou et al., 2023). Unlike traditional technologies, AI-integrated systems provide real-time, personalised feedback, offering learners greater flexibility, interactive support and unlimited practice opportunities that may not be feasible with human instructors (Fathi & Rahimi, 2024; Kuddus, 2022).

Additionally, advances in machine learning, Natural Language Processing (NLP), and Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) have increased the potential for even more tailored language learning experiences. MALL applications now provide learners with authentic, socially-situated speaking practice through interactive environments (Tapalova & Zhiyenbayeva, 2022). For instance, conversational AI agents, such as Google Assistant, can engage learners in spoken interactions and offer scaffolded feedback in low-pressure settings, compared to conventional classrooms (Chen et al., 2023; Istrate, 2018).

Specifically, in EFL contexts—where exposure to spoken English is often limited—MALL has shown promise in enhancing oral fluency. Empirical studies support this claim. Grimshaw and Cardoso (2018), for example, found that learners using the mobile game Spaceteam ESL demonstrated greater fluency gains than those in the control group. Similarly, Ahmed et al. (2022) reported significant improvements in speaking fluency among EFL learners who used Duolingo and WhatsApp, attributing these gains to the frequent, anxiety-free speaking opportunities

provided. These findings suggest that MALL facilitates the proceduralisation of language, a key factor in developing fluency.

However, a review of the literature reveals a predominant focus on structured tasks (e.g., read-aloud), with limited research on AI use in spontaneous speech involving open-ended responses (Zechner & Hsieh, 2024). In this regard, Rudnik (2024) distinguishes “traditional AI,” which operates according to preset rules, from “generative AI,” which can produce original content and support adaptive interaction. As generative tools become more widespread, users may mistakenly assume that all AI technologies possess such capabilities, despite many lacking the necessary functionality for spontaneous speech (Kaiser, 2024).

Perceptions towards MALL

Research has shown that learner perceptions play a crucial role in sustained engagement with technology for language learning (Gardner & Lambert, 1972). Overall, the literature reveals a generally positive attitude towards MALL. For instance, Van and Duong (2022) found that Vietnamese university students perceived MALL as useful, particularly for vocabulary and pronunciation, and found it easy to use. Similarly, Zou et al. (2023) reported that learners found AI-based speech evaluation tools to be enjoyable and helpful. However, they raised concerns about the potential for inaccurate feedback and a lack of human interaction.

In another study, Hoi and Mu (2021) investigated Vietnamese EFL students' expectations of teachers' roles in promoting MALL. Analysing survey data from 293 university learners using a Rasch-based path model, the study found that students valued teacher guidance on using mobile resources both in and beyond the classroom, suggesting that the successful implementation of MALL depends not only on technological appeal but also on pedagogical instruction.

Besides the positive feedback, there have been accounts of shortcomings in mobile applications. Learners reported dissatisfaction, mainly due to overly complex or technical feedback and poor interface design (An et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024). Another notable recurring issue is the difficulty in interacting with voice recognition systems, which frequently leads to frustration and disengagement (Dizon et al., 2022; McCrocklin, 2019).

Reviewing ELSA Speak, Loora, and Vocal Image applications, Kaiser (2024) noted that although features such as ASR and generative AI may enhance user

engagement, persistent challenges remain, particularly in providing accurate suprasegmental feedback and processing natural speech. ELSA Speak, for example, may support communicative competence but often misjudges connected speech and relies on simplistic indicators, such as loudness, to assess stress and rhythm, reflecting limited input from linguistics experts. Moreover, AI speech evaluation systems were reported to fall short of human listeners in recognising different accents and spontaneous speech, raising concerns about demotivating learners and reducing their confidence (Evers & Chen, 2020; Jeon, 2022; McCrocklin, 2019; Zou et al., 2023).

Research gaps and research questions

The review of the literature has shown that while several prior studies have explored the impact of MALL tools, including ELSA Speak, on English language learning, particularly pronunciation and speaking skills (e.g., Bashori et al., 2024; Ebadi & Ebadijalal, 2022; Rad, 2024), most studies are experimental or mixed methods, with limited focus on oral fluency specifically (Tavakoli & Hunter, 2018). Furthermore, little is known about the in-depth perceptions of Vietnamese EFL university students regarding ELSA Speak and the perceived usefulness of its individual features for developing fluency. Therefore, to address this gap, the present study adopts a qualitative case study approach to investigate these learners' experiences and perceptions, thereby contributing insights to the emerging field of AI-enhanced fluency development in MALL. The following two research questions were formulated to address the identified research gaps:

1. What are the valuable features of ELSA Speak to improve English oral fluency perceived by Vietnamese EFL university students?
2. What are Vietnamese EFL university students' general perceptions towards the advantages and disadvantages of using ELSA Speak for improving fluency?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current study employed a qualitative case study approach to conduct an in-depth exploration of learners' perceptions and experiences within a bounded context (van Lier, 2005). According to Duff (2010), qualitative research enables researchers to gain an understanding of complex issues without the intention of manipulating circumstances or proving a pre-established hypothesis. For this

reason, the qualitative approach was suitable for the current study, as it enabled an in-depth investigation of learners' perceptions and experiences when engaging with ELSA Speak for the development of oral fluency. The study focused on a group of seven Vietnamese EFL university students who voluntarily used the ELSA Speak app over four weeks. This design enables a deeper understanding of how learners interact with the app in their daily usage.

The study was first reviewed and approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee of the University of Sydney (Approval No. 2024/HE001278). Since the current study involved human participants, ethical considerations were addressed before data collection commenced and throughout the study. This aligned with Fraenkel et al. (2019), who suggested three important issues to be addressed in research: protecting participants from harm, ensuring confidentiality of research data, and considering the ethical implications of deceiving participants. Figure 1 summarises the detailed procedures for data collection and analysis undertaken in this study.

Figure 1. Research procedures

The pre-data collection stage involved preparing interview materials, obtaining ethics approval, recruiting participants, obtaining informed consent and conducting pilot interviews. The data collection phase included pre-interviews, diary entry and screen recording collection, and post-interviews. As shown here, data were collected through three primary instruments: semi-structured

interviews, reflective learner diaries, and screen recordings of app usage. In the post-data collection phase, all data were transcribed and translated in preparation for analysis. The data analysis phase employed thematic analysis, guided by Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase framework. To enhance the trustworthiness of the findings, intra-coder reliability checks were conducted, and data triangulation was carried out across the three data sources.

Research settings

After approval by the Human Research Ethics Committee of the University of Sydney, a recruitment advertisement, presented in both English and Vietnamese, was disseminated across Facebook pages and forums to engage potential participants, particularly students from universities across Vietnam. As the researcher was based in Australia while the participants were in Vietnam, the study was conducted entirely online, utilising platforms such as Zoom and Zalo Messenger, a widely used local application predominant among Vietnamese people for communication. This online approach was designed to facilitate broader geographic reach and to include a more diverse range of participants from various majors and universities across Vietnam, potentially encompassing a wider range of accents, educational backgrounds, and language learning experiences, and offering richer insights into the investigated questions.

Research participants

Initially, eight EFL students submitted their signed Participant Consent Form. However, one participant withdrew due to personal reasons, resulting in a final sample of seven Vietnamese EFL university students (four females and three males) for the current study. Table 1 presents detailed information about the participants.

Table 1. *Participants' demography*

Name	Gender	Grade	Major	Goals
Participant 1	Male	Year 4	Information Technology (IT)	Effectively communicate in the workplace Improve TOEIC scores
Participant 2	Female	Year 2	Economics	Respond more quickly and fluently without hesitation
Participant 3	Male	Year 1	Marketing - Finance	Enter a higher-level IELTS preparation class
Participant 4	Female	Year 2	English Language	Fluent and confident English communication Improve IELTS scores
Participant 5	Female	Year 1	English Language	Increase English levels and be more confident in communication
Participant 6	Male	Year 2	Computing	Improve speaking skills for future interaction and negotiation at work Succeed in a global work environment Improve IELTS Speaking scores
Participant 8	Female	Year 3	Chinese Language	Achieve a targeted IELTS score Improve English pronunciation

As depicted in this table, the participant group encompassed a wide range of academic levels, ranging from first-year undergraduates to those in their final year. The diversity extended to their fields of study, with three participants majoring in Languages, two each in Economics, Marketing, and Finance, and an additional two in Computing and Information Technology. The participants' motivations for

learning English varied considerably although the primary focus was on enhancing oral proficiency. These can be categorised into short-term goals, such as achieving a specific test score, and long-term goals, including professional development and personal growth.

Research instruments and techniques

The current study employed four main instruments for data collection, which are presented in detail as follows.

The ELSA Speak application

The current study employed an AI-assisted application called ELSA Speak, specifically designed to support language learners' oral proficiency. The tool is designed to help users enhance their English-speaking skills, enabling them to communicate with clarity, fluency, and confidence (Karim et al., 2023). Figure 2 illustrates the ELSA Speak interface, highlighting its key features.

Figure 1. Interface of ELSA Speak and its features

As illustrated in Figure 2, ELSA Speak incorporates an extensive array of features, including 'ELSA AI Conversation', 'Practice Daily Lessons', 'Improve Pronunciation', 'Study by Topic', 'Earn a Certificate', 'Games and more'. According to ELSA Speak (n.d.), the application's standout functionalities encompass AI role-plays, an advanced AI coach, AI feedback and progress tracking, over 8,000 concise lessons, a personalised AI-guided learning pathway, a bilingual AI tutor, guided practice,

transcripts accompanied by vocabulary suggestions, and certificate courses, among others.

Given that the current study focuses on English oral fluency, the first research question aimed to explore which of these features participants perceived as most useful for improving their fluency proficiency. To address this, participants were asked to spend 20 to 30 minutes daily learning with ELSA Speak over four weeks, exploring the application's various functionalities. They were then asked to document their experiences, noting the usefulness of specific features and the application's advantages and disadvantages, in daily diaries and post-study interviews.

Semi-structured interviews

According to Yin (2015), semi-structured or open-ended interviews are a flexible yet focused form of qualitative interviewing in which researchers prepare a predetermined set of topics or questions, while allowing participants to guide the sequence and depth of discussion. This method is particularly suitable for the present study, as it enables participants to elaborate on their unique perspectives while allowing the researcher to gain a deeper understanding of their views on specific features, usage behaviours, and emotional responses. Besides that, its adaptability accommodates online formats and supports triangulation with other qualitative data sources (Seale, 1999). Noting the importance of a balanced exchange, Ezzy (2010) stressed that effective interviews should be shaped neither by the interviewer's dominance nor the interviewee's personal agenda. In line with this, the researcher made a conscious effort to build rapport, listen attentively, follow up, and elicit detailed responses. Following the interviews, audio recordings were transcribed and translated from Vietnamese to English and then analysed thematically.

Diaries

Given the aim of this study—to explore learners' perceptions and experiences as they engage with the AI-mediated ELSA Speak application—diary methods are particularly well-suited. Three key rationales underpin this appropriateness. Firstly, diary methods are a valuable data collection tool in applied linguistics and language learning research, adept at capturing participants' personal experiences, thoughts, and behaviours in real-time contexts (Porto, 2007). In this regard, Dörnyei (2007) noted that diaries enable participants to record language-related activities and reflect on their learning processes, providing access to their inner

thoughts on constructs such as motivation, self-regulation, anxiety, and autonomy, which can be challenging to capture through other methods or tools. Moreover, the reflective nature of diaries allows participants to articulate unique insights without the researcher needing to resort to indirect methods to access comparable thoughts (Dörnyei, 2007).

The diary method, while offering significant advantages, presented challenges that must be addressed. These included the substantial time and effort required from participants, which might result in incomplete or low-quality entries (Bolger et al., 2003), literacy demands, particularly for participants writing in a non-native language (Rose, 2020) and the potential for recall bias when entries are delayed (Carson & Longhini, 2002). To reduce the time and effort burden on participants, clear instructions, the expected time commitment (20-30 mins per day), guiding questions and introductory training were provided prior to data collection. To address literacy demands, participants were permitted to write in their native language, Vietnamese, thereby reducing linguistic barriers. As an example, an excerpt of Participant 2's writing in Vietnamese is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Excerpt of participant 2's written reflections

Which activity do I find useful to improve my fluency? Why? (Tôi thấy hoạt động nào hữu ích để cải thiện khả năng nói trôi chảy của mình? Tại sao?)

Em thấy việc luyện nói shadowing về học tập, cuộc sống, sở thích,.. giúp em đỡ nhàm chán, hứng thú hơn với việc tự nói tiếng anh. Từ đó luyện được phản xạ và độ trôi chảy nói tiếng anh. Vì trong đoạn hội thoại có sẵn câu thoại trả lời, em biết thêm nhiều cách diễn đạt trong từng tình huống: như là khi đi ra sân bay kiểm tra hành lý nói như nào, tập sở thích mới trong dịch Covid,..

Luyện qua đoạn hội thoại thì mình vừa nghe được tông giọng, âm điệu như nào để bắt chước theo cho hợp lý.

Finally, to mitigate recall bias, as recommended by Ma and Oxford (2014), reminders were sent to participants to complete their diary entries immediately

after each practice session. These measures were designed to ensure the validity and reliability of the data collected through the diary method.

Screen recordings

According to Heycke and Spitzer (2019), screen recordings provide a powerful means of capturing real-time interactions in digital learning environments. This instrument enhances the transparency and reproducibility of research by preserving visual and procedural details that are often omitted from written reports. In the present study, screen recordings were used to document participants' multimodal interactions—including on-screen navigation, typing behaviour, and engagement with interface features—during their use of the ELSA Speak app. These forms of interaction would have been difficult to access through observations or interviews alone. Additionally, due to practical constraints, particularly the distance between the participants and the researcher, it was not feasible to observe the practice sessions in person. As such, screen recordings offered an alternative means of capturing detailed usage behaviour over time. The data collected from these recordings were later triangulated with diary entries to enhance the trustworthiness of the findings.

Despite their advantages, screen recordings also posed challenges, particularly regarding data privacy and the technical limitations associated with the large storage requirements of video files (Ho, 2021). To address these concerns, informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection, and no video of participants' faces was recorded; only the mobile device screen during app use was captured. Furthermore, all data were securely stored in the University of Sydney's Research Data Storage system, with sufficient storage and access restricted solely to the researcher.

DATA ANALYSIS

Thematic analysis

To answer the two research questions, the current study employed thematic analysis (TA) as the primary method of data analysis. As defined by Braun and Clarke (2022), TA is a flexible yet systematic approach for identifying and interpreting meaningful patterns within a dataset, which enables researchers to analyse both manifest and latent meanings relevant to the research questions. TA can be positioned along a continuum between inductive and deductive approaches.

This was clarified by Braun and Clarke (2006). Whereas a deductive (top-down) approach applies pre-existing concepts to interpret data, an inductive (bottom-up) approach derives codes and themes directly from the data, prioritising participants' reported experiences. Given the exploratory nature of a case study, the current study primarily adopted an inductive approach to capture participants' authentic experiences and perceptions, free from predetermined analytical concepts. This analysis process, following Braun and Clarke's (2022) six-phase framework, is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. *Thematic analysis stages (adopted from Braun and Clarke, 2022)*

As illustrated in Figure 4, the first TA phase involved the researcher getting thoroughly familiar with the data. Participants' interviews were transcribed and checked for accuracy. Both the interview transcripts and diary entries were then translated from Vietnamese into English. This process was relatively time-intensive, with the pre- and post-interview transcripts totalling 22,572 words and the diaries comprising 24,668 words. Following this, the researcher engaged in multiple readings of all transcripts and diaries to gain an overall impression of the dataset before coding, or, in other words, systematically analysing the data by identifying and labelling meaningful items relevant to the research questions. The computer software NVivo was utilised in this process for more efficient coding. Table 2 shows a sample of codes generated after the initial round of data analysis.

Table 2. An example of initial codes

Interview transcripts and diaries	Codes
<p>“<u>Study by Topic</u> allows me to <u>speak on the themes</u>. Its library is quite large, so I learned more <u>words by topic</u>. I think that increases the length of the sentences I say. This part also allows me to <u>choose the topic freely</u>. For example, if I'm tired, I'll choose something fun. If I'm not tired, I'll choose something difficult.” (Participant 6)</p>	<p>Perceived useful features: Study by topic Practice with themes Learn topical vocabulary Freedom to choose topics</p>
<p>“The <u>conversation practice was most useful to me</u> because it <u>simulated real talking situations</u>. It helps me practice <u>using different phrases in context</u>, which in turn helps me speak <u>more fluently and confidently</u>. In addition, it also helps me practice taking long breaths to <u>speak a long paragraph</u>.</p> <p>I found the feedback very helpful. The <u>feedback is very detailed</u> and <u>tells me exactly</u> which sounds or words I need to improve. I appreciate <u>feedback that gives me a score</u>, so I can track my progress and understand where I need to focus.” (Participant 1)</p>	<p>Perceived useful features: Conversation Simulate real conversations Practice using language in contexts More fluent More confident Practice speaking at length Detailed feedback Exact feedback Quantified feedback</p>
<p>“And I think Elsa's voice recognition is better, but <u>when you're in an environment where it's just a little bit noisy</u>, and when you need to study on the app, the <u>results are affected quite a lot</u>.” (Participant 4)</p>	<p>Inaccuracies in recognition due to background noise</p>

The analysis then advanced through multiple rounds of coding. After that, related codes were grouped and organised into themes that reflect meaningful patterns across the dataset in relation to the research questions (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Phases four and five of the thematic analysis focused on reviewing and refining

themes. This process was recursive as the researcher navigated back and forth between phases. Table 3 depicts how the themes addressing RQ2 were derived.

Table 3. *An example of emerging themes for RQ2*

Themes	Sub-themes	Codes
Perceived advantages	Increase trust and positivity towards AI-assisted learning	Can speak at length & with less hesitation
		Can speak spontaneously & with better intonation
		Improved communication skills
		Improved pronunciation - timely error correction
		Increased confidence
		Increased grammar accuracy
		Increased interest in practising speaking
		Increased vocabulary
		Personalised practice & feedback

Table 3. (continued)

Themes	Sub-themes	Codes
Perceived advantages	Enhance learning experience	Allow for repetition and multiple practice
		Help build learning habits
		Highlight strengths and weaknesses
		Integrate the functions of many apps into one
		Less pressure than speaking with humans
		Offer fun, enjoyable learning
	Provide an English speaking environment	Can learn how to ask questions
		Offer a systematic approach for learning
		Prepare for real-life interactions
		Various functions and topics for learning
	Offer detailed feedback	Detailed feedback with scores and percentages
		Display of the IPA recognition system for pronunciation adjustments
		More personalised feedback vs feedback in the classroom
		Suggestions for better phrases or vocab

Table 3. (continued)

Themes	Sub-themes	Codes
Perceived disadvantages	Learning-related challenges	Lack progress tracking - cannot review past lessons
		Limited practice reminders
		General feedback for fluency
		Strict/rigid/mechanical feedback
	Technical challenges	Delayed responses
		Fail to recognise voice
		Inaccuracies due to background noise
		Inconsistent user interface
		Using tricks to bypass the app's error spotting
	Content-related challenges	Avoid specialised topics - lack of knowledge
		Disconnection between the app and real life

As shown in Table 3, the two main themes for RQ2 were developed through the integration of multiple sub-themes, each comprising several related codes. King (2004) recommended that themes should not be considered final until all data have been thoroughly reviewed and all coding has been checked at least twice. In line with this recommendation, the coding process in the current study was conducted twice to ensure intra-coder reliability (Révész, 2023), and the themes were revisited multiple times to identify meaningful insights from the dataset.

The last stage of data analysis involved constructing a coherent narrative from all the themes to address the research questions, in which arguments were developed based on the researcher's interpretative analysis with data extracts integrated to support and illustrate key points.

Data triangulation

Data triangulation refers to the use of multiple sources of data or methods of data collection to investigate the same research phenomenon from different perspectives (Flick, 2018). This method is suitable for this research because it enables a more holistic exploration of learner engagement with the ELSA application. For example, screen recordings captured participants' actual interactions with the app's interface, while diary entries offered reflective insights. Diary accounts (what participants reported) were cross-verified with screen recordings (what participants did) to ensure reliability and reduce potential biases. Table 4 illustrates how these data sources were triangulated to address Research Question 1.

Table 3. An example of data triangulation

Theme	Screen recordings	Diary entries	Confirm/ Contradict
Study by Topic	<p>Participant 1 practised with topic-based lessons and long sentences.</p> <p>The screenshot shows a speech bubble with a sad face and the text 'Gần đúng' (Almost correct) and 'Bạn nói giống người bản xứ 66%' (You speak like a native 66%). Below it, the sentence 'My biggest wish is to improve my English.' is written in green and red. The phonetic transcription is '/maɪ ˈbɪ.gɪst wɪʃ ɪz tə ɪmˈpruːv maɪ ˈɪŋ.g.lɪʃ/'. There are icons for play, volume, and share. At the bottom, it says 'Mong muốn lớn nhất của tôi là cải thiện tiếng Anh.'</p>	<p>"I did daily practice exercises and then did pronunciation exercises and <u>studied by topics</u>. I find that the whole-sentence reading activity helped <u>me speak more fluently</u>. From there, I know where I should improve." (Participant 1)</p>	Confirm

Table 4. (continued)

Theme	Screen recordings	Diary entries	Confirm/ Contradict
Improve Pronunciation	<p>Participant 3 practised with the pronunciation feature for 15 minutes.</p>	<p>“Today I practised <u>Pronunciation</u> and <u>Intonation</u>. I still want to improve my pronunciation because <u>it is essential in communication.</u>” (Participant 3)</p>	Confirm
Video Conversation	<p>Participant 3 spent 20 minutes practising with a video conversation on a shopping topic.</p>	<p>“Today I practised the <u>Video Conversation</u> feature. There is an additional video demonstration. I find that practising shadowing about studies, life, hobbies, etc., helps me feel less bored. From there, you can practice your reflexes and fluency in speaking English.” (Participant 2)</p>	Confirm

As shown in Table 4, 'Study by Topic' was identified in both the screen recording and the diary entry of Participant 1. The participant's engagement with topic-based lessons and sentence-reading activities, as observed in the recording, corroborated their self-reported learning activities, resulting in a "Confirm" classification. Conversely, if discrepancies were found between data sources, the classification would be marked as "Contradict." Similar patterns of confirmation were observed for "*Improve Pronunciation*" (Participant 3) and "*Video Conversation*" (Participant 2).

Trustworthiness

In qualitative research, trustworthiness is a concept introduced by Guba and Lincoln (1982) to replace notions of validity and reliability, which are rooted in positivist paradigms. Trustworthiness denotes the extent to which a study persuasively establishes the credibility of its findings. To ensure trustworthiness, the present study adhered to the following four critical criteria proposed by Lincoln and Guba (1985): Credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability.

Credibility was ensured through multiple strategies. First, triangulating data sources—interviews, screen recordings, and diary entries—provided a clearer understanding of participants' perspectives. Prolonged engagement (i.e., a four-week data collection period) enabled the researcher to build rapport, better understand learners' behaviour, and minimise the possibility of data distortions arising from initial communications (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Additionally, participants were allowed to write diary entries in Vietnamese to reduce linguistic barriers, thereby encouraging more authentic self-reports in the data.

Transferability was addressed through a thick description of the research setting, participant background, and the context in which the ELSA Speak app was used. This allows readers to judge the extent to which the findings might apply to similar contexts involving EFL learners and mobile-assisted language learning. Subsequently, *dependability* was enhanced through transparent documentation of the research procedures. Particularly, data analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2022) thematic analysis, and coding was conducted and checked multiple times to ensure consistency and intra-coder reliability (Révész, 2023).

Finally, *confirmability* was established by connecting findings directly to the data through the inclusion of participant quotations and contextual descriptions. The use of multiple data sources enabled the researcher to construct themes from

participants' reports and actions, rather than imposing pre-existing assumptions. In line with Lincoln and Guba (1985), this approach assures readers that the research was conducted honestly and that the findings accurately reflect participants' voices and experiences.

FINDINGS

Research question (RQ) 1: What are perceived as functional features of ELSA Speak to improve English oral fluency by Vietnamese EFL university students?

The ELSA Speak application offers a range of features to support learners in developing various skills. Given that the current study focuses on English oral fluency, it is crucial to identify the ELSA Speak features that participants perceive as most beneficial for supporting this specific aspect of their language proficiency.

In the current study, participants used the ELSA Speak application over four weeks and recorded their experiences through device screen recordings, daily journal entries, and semi-structured interviews. Qualitative data analysis identified 13 ELSA Speak features that participants perceived as beneficial for improving oral fluency. These features are presented in Table 5, along with the frequency of mentions and the number of participants who referred to each.

Due to word limit constraints and the need for analytical depth, the answer to RQ1 focuses on the six most frequently referenced features: Study by Topic, Improve Pronunciation, ELSA AI Conversation, Practice Daily Lessons, Earn a Certificate – IELTS, and Conversation. However, it is important to note that excluding these features from this discussion does not imply their irrelevance. Participants meaningfully referenced all thirteen features, but the six presented here were mentioned more consistently, with some supported by more substantial data from both interviews and journal entries.

Table 6 summarises the key findings and ranks the six features in descending order of the number of times a feature is mentioned. Although the frequency of mentions may reflect the prevalence of these features in the study, it does not necessarily imply that one feature is more significant than others. Instead, the frequency may suggest a tendency for participants to perceive one feature as more or less relevant to them.

Table 5. Overview of ELSA Speak features identified as useful for improving oral fluency

Features	Number of mentions	Number of participants who mentioned a feature
Study by Topic	37	6
Improve Pronunciation	30	6
ELSA AI Conversation	25	5
Practice Daily Lessons	23	6
Earn a Certificate - IELTS	16	3
Conversation	14	3
Tests	3	2
Listening	3	2
Video Conversation	3	1
Study Sets	2	1
Speech Analysis	1	1
Unscrambling Words	1	1
Word Stress	1	1

Table 6. Perceived useful features of ELSA Speak for improving English oral fluency

Features	Summary of participants' comments	Examples
Study by Topic (37 mentions)	Participants found studying by topic particularly useful for developing their fluency through vocabulary improvement and practice with a range of themes.	<p>“Study by Topic allows me to speak on the themes. Its library is quite large, so I <u>learned more words by topic</u>. I think <u>that increases the length of the sentences</u> I say. This part also <u>allows me to choose the topic freely</u>. For example, if I'm tired, I'll choose something fun. If I'm not tired, I'll choose something difficult.” (Participant 6)</p> <p>“I think the activity that I found most useful to improve my fluency was studying by topic. One time, I studied online dating. <u>I felt like I was practising speaking with a real person</u>. When I practised speaking on this topic, I <u>accumulated not only vocabulary but also knowledge</u>.” (Participant 8)</p>

Table 6. (continued)

Features	Summary of participants' comments	Examples
Improve Pronunciation (30 mentions)	Participants repeatedly reported using the app to practice final sounds, stress, intonation, and specific phonemes. The app is useful for identifying and correcting their mistakes.	<p>“I want to <u>improve my pronunciation</u> because it is very <u>important in communication.</u>” (Participant 3)</p> <p>“Today I only had time for Daily Practice and Pronunciation Improvement (PI), which was useful <u>when I found myself making a serious mistake.</u>” (Participant 6)</p>
ELSA AI Conversation (25 mentions)	Participants highlighted the usefulness of interacting with AI, which provided natural and responsive practice environments. The AI feature was considered a helpful and engaging tool, offering role-play scenarios and also marking grammar and vocabulary for self-assessment.	<p>“<u>It trains me to think about what I need to say</u> in a certain situation. And if there are some ideas that I don't know how to express, I will go back to ELSA AI Conversations and <u>practice some words that I don't know.</u>” (Participant 3)</p> <p>“But <u>in this conversation section, ELSA fixes long sentences</u> and it <u>counts fluency in its scoring</u> as well. Other parts do not have criteria for fluency.” (Participant 5)</p>

Table 6. (continued)

Features	Summary of participants' comments	Examples
Practice Daily Lessons (23 mentions)	Participants reported that they frequently used Practice Daily, combined with ELSA AI and Study by Topic, to address specific weaknesses such as pronunciation or fluency.	<p>“Today I did the Practice Daily. <u>Reading whole sentences activity helped me speak more fluently.</u> It causes me to <u>catch my breath and focus more.</u>” (Participant 1)</p> <p>“I did Practice Daily because I wanted to <u>focus on improving my pronunciation weaknesses,</u> such as the /dz/ sound.” (Participant 4)</p>
Earn a certificate - IELTS (16 mentions)	Participants reported consistently using several lessons from the "Introduction to IELTS Band 6" and "Band 7" courses to enhance their speaking skills and achieve a higher test score.	<p>“Today I <u>practised with IELTS Speaking.</u> I took the opportunity to try talking to AI to see if I could react quickly. Today I practised the topic "talking about a summer trip". The <u>feedback was good; it told me what level I was at.</u>” (Participant 2)</p> <p>“I want to <u>continue using this activity to improve my actual IELTS score.</u>” (Participant 4)</p>

Table 6. (continued)

Features	Summary of participants' comments	Examples
Conversation (14 mentions)	Participants mentioned using Conversations to practice dialogue skills. There are specific topics, such as "Talk to your Colleagues" and "Talking to the Boss", where they can revisit vocabulary and useful phrases and integrate conversations into broader exercises involving pronunciation and stress.	"I found that practising dialogues was the most helpful for me because <u>I practised topics related to everyday life.</u> The dialogues were <u>about sharing experiences about my loved ones,</u> which helped me <u>make connections and think faster</u> while speaking." (Participant 5)

As shown in Table 6, the most frequently cited features were 'Study by Topic', followed by 'Improve Pronunciation' and 'ELSA AI Conversation.' Among these, 'Study by Topic' and 'ELSA AI Conversation' stood out in both journal and interview data and were observed to support fluency in different ways. These were followed by 'Practice Daily Lessons', 'Earn a Certificate – IELTS' and 'Conversation', which are explained in more detail below.

Study by Topic

Six out of seven participants appreciated 'Study by Topic' for its flexibility in choosing themes that align with their interests, for building vocabulary within specific topics, and for acquiring additional knowledge while simultaneously practising their English skills. As illustrated in Table 6, Participant 1 noted that ELSA Speak helped them "practice using different phrases in context," which contributed to their speaking "more fluently and confidently." Participant 8 found 'Study by Topic' to be the most useful activity for them, sharing that when practising a theme like online dating, they "felt like [they were] practising speaking with a real person" and were able to "accumulate not only vocabulary but also knowledge."

Notably, Participant 6 appreciated the feature's thematic structure and flexibility, explaining that its large topic library allowed them to “learn more words by topics,” which they believed helped “increase the length of the sentences” they could produce. This result is meaningful because it aligns with the notion in previous research (e.g., Little, 2004; Ushioda, 2011) that a sense of control and empowerment in their own learning processes is likely to intrinsically motivate learners to persist in their learning.

Improve Pronunciation

Table 6 shows that the ‘Improve Pronunciation’ feature was valued for providing focused feedback on discrete phonological elements such as final sounds, stress, and intonation. Six participants reported using this to identify and correct pronunciation errors that impeded their fluency. Specifically, Participant 3 stated, “I want to improve my pronunciation because it is very important in communication.” This view was echoed by Participant 6, who found this feature particularly useful for addressing serious errors during practice.

ELSA AI conversation

Although ‘ELSA AI Conversation’ was not mentioned as frequently as ‘Study by Topic’ or ‘Improve Pronunciation’ during the 4-week observation and diary entries, it was highlighted by five out of seven participants as significantly useful for improving their fluency during the post-interviews. This was largely attributed to its capacity to simulate realistic, interactive dialogues with an AI interlocutor, encouraging learners to think in the target language and practise unfamiliar words in real-life contexts.

As shown in Table 6, Participant 2 reported practising with the feature by “chatting with a virtual speaker” and appreciated that the AI “responded to [their] statements.” Participant 8 described a similar experience, stating that “it was also like my friend, talking with me very naturally and quickly.” For Participant 3, the feature encouraged spontaneous thinking and allowed for iterative practice: “It trains me to think about what I need to say in a certain situation,” and when struggling with vocabulary, they would “go back to ‘ELSA AI Conversations’ and practice some words... then go back and practice again.” This finding is significant because it confirms prior studies’ findings on improving learners’ spoken proficiency through fostering authentic and spontaneous conversations (Jung Youn, 2023; Tavakoli et al., 2020).

Participant 5 also emphasised that, unlike other features which focus primarily on word-level pronunciation, 'ELSA AI Conversation' provided feedback on longer utterances and incorporated "fluency in its scoring," which they noted was "not available in other parts." This outcome contributes to prior research on the usefulness of conversational AI in delivering such feedback, focusing on a broader spectrum of language proficiency dimensions rather than exclusively on pronunciation (Ji et al., 2022; Zechner & Hsieh, 2024), thereby demonstrably enhancing learner engagement and language learning outcomes.

Practice Daily Lessons

Reported by six of seven participants, the 'Practice Daily Lessons' feature was typically used in conjunction with others, particularly to build study habits and target specific weaknesses. Participant 1 reported that reading whole sentences helped enhance fluency, explaining that it required them to "catch [their] breath and focus more." Similarly, Participant 4 used the feature to target specific pronunciation challenges, such as the /dʒ/ sound. Participant 6 highlighted the motivating design of the activity, stating, "There is no excuse to stop grinding on Daily Practice," and described the exercises as "somewhat crucial." These insights suggest that Daily Practice supported both sustained engagement and targeted improvement in pronunciation.

On the one hand, the 'Improve Pronunciation' feature provided targeted feedback on specific phonological elements, helping learners identify and address individual errors. On the other hand, the 'Practice Daily Lessons' feature reinforced pronunciation through regular, structured activities, thereby helping learners build consistency and motivation in their study routines. On the other hand, these two features complement each other by supporting both accuracy and fluency in learners' speaking development. This suggests that participants viewed pronunciation accuracy as a key component of fluency development, aligning with previous research on teachers' and learners' perceptions of oral fluency (Khanh & Huynh, 2022).

Earn a Certificate – IELTS

'Earn a Certificate – IELTS' was cited by three participants preparing for standardised speaking tests and was valued for its structured progression and scoring system, which allowed users to measure their performance levels and track improvements. Participant 2 used the feature to test their spontaneous speaking ability, explaining, "I took the opportunity to try talking to AI to see if I

could react quickly,” and noted that the feedback was useful for identifying their speaking level. Participant 4 expressed a clear intention to continue using this activity, stating, “I want to continue using this activity to improve my actual IELTS score.” These responses suggest that the feature not only supported speaking fluency but also served as a motivational tool for learners who aim to succeed in standardised tests such as IELTS.

Conversation

The final feature presented in Table 6 is ‘Conversation’, reported by three out of seven participants. Unlike ‘ELSA AI Conversation’, which allows free responses without models and provides feedback on overall performance, pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar, the ‘Conversation’ feature offers sample dialogues for users to repeat, followed by immediate, percentage-based accuracy feedback. Participant 5 reflected that this feature helped them “think faster while speaking,” while Participant 8 noted its usefulness as a preparatory step for more open-ended tasks, stating that when using ‘ELSA AI Conversation’, “I couldn’t think of any ideas... I felt like I was stuck,” and therefore preferred practising with structured dialogues first.

In summary, the current findings underscore the importance of integrating both activities that require learners to express their communicative intent in realistic interactional scenarios and tasks that focus on accuracy in AI-assisted language learning. This is consistent with prior research emphasising the role of simulated interaction, targeted pronunciation feedback, and personalised learning in developing oral fluency (e.g., Ebadi & Ebadijalal, 2022; Kormos & Dénes, 2004) as well as with the *Review of previous research* section.

Research question 2: What are Vietnamese EFL university students’ general perceptions towards the advantages and disadvantages of using ELSA Speak for improving fluency?

While Research Question 1 focused on the specific features of ELSA Speak perceived as useful for fluency development, Research Question 2 expands the scope to explore participants’ broader experiences using the app, thereby enabling the optimisation of its beneficial features while addressing its limitations. It is essential to note that the term “useful features” in RQ1 refers to components of the application (e.g., Study by Topic, Improve Pronunciation), whereas in RQ2, “advantages” and “disadvantages” refer to learners’ experiences—the processes of engaging with ELSA Speak over time.

The findings for RQ2 presented in this section are based on a content analysis of participants' interview transcripts and journal entries, triangulated with screen recordings of participants' practice over the four-week study. Thematically coded, the combined data reveal patterns highlighting both the app's benefits and limitations. Figure 5 presents a summary of these findings.

Figure 5. Advantages and disadvantages of using ELSA Speak for developing English oral fluency as perceived by the participants

Advantages of ELSA Speak

Figure 5 illustrates four key advantages that emerged from the analysis: increased trust and positivity toward AI-assisted learning, enhanced learning experience, provision of an English-speaking environment, and detailed feedback. In the subsequent paragraphs, each of these themes will be discussed in more detail, accompanied by notable excerpts from the participants.

Increase trust and positivity towards AI-assisted learning

First of all, all participants reported that using ELSA Speak has increased their trust in the tool and helped them have a more favourable perception of employing AI-supported technology for learning purposes, as Participant 1 asserted, "My trust in the app has increased. I think I am more positive about practising with an app than before."

This phenomenon may be attributed to the participants' experiences of not only improvements in grammatical and lexical accuracy, pronunciation, and fluency, but also an increase in their interest and confidence in speaking, especially in articulating extended sentences. Along this line, Participant 4 shared:

I have seen some improvements. In ELSA AI, I feel like I'm talking to a real person. That's also a way for me to be more confident when I practice. I feel less nervous when I'm talking to people. I can see this very clearly in my interactions in English class at school.

It is noted that following a period of practice with the ELSA Speak application, Participant 4 experienced a noticeable increase in confidence and a decrease in nervousness in real-life interactions. This finding is significant because it reveals an app's impact beyond controlled practice sessions, extending to real-life communication skills. Besides that, it corroborates prior research on the relationship between AI-assisted language learning and students' affective factors, encompassing constructs such as confidence and motivation (Wang et al., 2024).

Enhance learning experience

As seen from Figure 5, all participants appreciated the ELSA Speak app's ability to enhance their learning experience. This is because it provides them with a range of functions and topics, presented in a systematic, structured manner. On this point, Participant 5 reported, "There are so many lessons in the app, and it covers a whole range of speaking skills. Every time I come in, I will have a different practice." Participant 2 added, "ELSA suggests a systematic approach, like the IELTS part has lessons for band 6.0 to band 9.0. It is very clear." This remark underscores the ability of the application to deliver a scaffolded learning experience by systematically sequencing the lessons with progressively increasing difficult levels.

The findings are consistent with existing research exploring the role of AI-powered tools in language education. Such tools demonstrate the capacity to personalise language learning by providing quantitative assessments of speaking performance, while also assessing learners' weaknesses, strengths and knowledge gaps to suggest practices that meet their needs (e.g., Ebadi & Ebadijalal, 2022; Wang et al., 2023).

Provide an English speaking environment

The analysis also revealed that seven participants agreed that ELSA Speak provided an environment for them to practice speaking English, which they often found lacking in both their classrooms and social settings in Vietnam. Participant 8 revisited their experience:

[...] When I was in high school, I just studied grammar, reading, writing, etc. I didn't practice speaking. I didn't have a good environment. Now, when I started practising with ELSA, I realised I was speaking every day. It not only formed a habit for me but also helped me correct my pronunciation and speak more fluently. I used to stumble a lot, but now I can speak more fluently.

This indicates that, through the platform, Participant 8 benefited from an environment that allowed them to practice speaking daily, which contributed to the development of their habit, improved pronunciation, and enhanced overall fluency, with reduced hesitation. This insight is noteworthy because it echoes earlier research by de Jong and Perfetti (2011), who stressed that repeated practice is necessary for proceduralisation, making speaking automatic and improving fluency.

Offer more detailed feedback

Finally, six participants indicated that ELSA Speak offered more detailed and comprehensive feedback, particularly compared to human teachers or other applications. Participant 2 recounted, "ELSA AI helps me remember the old lessons and it also gives me good feedback. It's much more detailed than the ChatGPT app on my mobile phone." Participant 8 asserted their experiences as follows:

The feedback for me was wonderful. When I come across a sentence I don't know how to say, ELSA will provide me with a sample sentence that includes pronunciation and stress guidance. After I finish speaking, it will give me a percentage indicating how well I performed. This is something I rarely encountered when I was studying in school and receiving too general comments from teachers or friends.

It can be observed that the participant benefited from a distinct advantage of ELSA Speak: providing learners with sample models and quantitative performance metrics, such as percentage scores. This contrasts with traditional classroom

settings in countries such as Vietnam, where teacher or peer feedback may be less specific. This was again stressed by Participant 2:

ELSA Speak's feedback is detailed, clearly outlining percentages and guidance on how to improve. Compared to the reality of going to school, teachers often focus on our listening and understanding of what they say, and the class is quite crowded, so we don't get much feedback on fluency and pronunciation. Besides, I don't often practise speaking in class, and when I do, it's just a little, so real-life feedback is insignificant. That's why studying at home with Elsa Speak helps me gain a deeper appreciation.

Disadvantages of ELSA Speak

Despite the advantages presented above, the data analysis also identified several limitations of the ELSA Speak application. As seen in Figure 5, three prominent themes include learning-related, technical and content-related challenges. These themes will be presented in greater detail in the following sections, with direct quotes from participants.

Learning-related challenges

As shown in Figure 5, challenges with using ELSA Speak for learning (e.g., inability to track past learning history, lack of reminders, overly general or overly rigid feedback) were reported by 6 participants. Among these, three participants highlighted the lack of records for completed lessons, making it difficult to review past exercises or track improvements. Regarding this, Participant 3 shared, "For the disadvantage, I cannot find the history of what I learned the previous day. It's hard to follow up the next day." Similarly, Participant 2 asserted that:

ELSA AI doesn't store the past lessons. Sometimes, I want to go back and see if I have improved, or if I've used a lot of words I've just learnt; there are no records. If I forget to take a picture, I won't be able to see it again. Also, many topics for ELSA AI Conversations change daily and are not fixed. So, if I revisit the app another day, that topic will no longer be there. I can't go back and practice that topic again.

What has been observed from these participants' recounts is that ELSA Speak appears limited in its capacity to support long-term learning. Indeed, its lack of records of learning history has been demonstrated to have inhibited learners from

revisiting and reviewing previous lessons and from practising certain content and reinforcing their skills.

This finding may contribute to existing research by addressing longer-term use of an application. This is unlike studies with only brief interventions - e.g., one hour with Google Assistant (Chen et al., 2023) or six hours with speech recognition websites (Bashori et al., 2024) - which may be biased due to novelty effects, where initial excitement with a technology can lead to better outcomes than those produced by sustained use (van den Berghe et al., 2019).

Technical challenges

The second challenge, as depicted in Figure 5, concerns the technical functionality of ELSA Speak, as highlighted by four participants. In particular, a noticeable delay was reported in registering user input. Concerning this, Participant 6 pointed out:

Sometimes the buttons lag. For example, sometimes I complete multiple-choice questions (MCQs), and the app does not receive the answer I choose until 3 seconds later. It was a bit weird. Three seconds felt so long.

Being a student specialising in computer science, Participant 6 provided further insight into the cause of this delay:

The bad thing is that the user interface is not synchronised. For example, in this lesson, the interface is A. In the other lesson, the interface is B. So, when you use it, the experience is not very good. When I first opened the app, I had to search for a long time before I found the ELSA AI function. I think the reason is that the app doesn't have a guide for its interface. It doesn't tell you what each button does.

Based on Participant 6's observations, the application's design remains limited, with noticeable technical delays, inconsistent interfaces, and insufficient user guidance, which may eventually undermine user satisfaction and experience. This aligns with findings reported in prior studies, such as Jeon (2022).

Another critical issue is the accuracy of ELSA Speak's speech recognition function. Relatedly, Participant 8 remarked, "Although I have practised the sound, sometimes four times, five times, it still marks my pronunciation wrong. In such a case, I will move on and not practise anymore." Similarly, Participant 2 reported,

“When you're in an environment where it's a little bit noisy, and when you need to study on the app, the results are affected quite a lot.”

Along the same line, but more strikingly, Participant 1 underscored a major problem with how the app assesses pronunciation, yet prioritises volume over correct syllable stress, which led to their diminishing interest in continuing to use the app:

The biggest disadvantage is that when it comes to stressing the syllables, you don't have to stress them properly. Instead, you only need to read them really loud and it will let you pass. It just lets go of the mistakes. When I discovered that loophole, I lost interest. I don't want to do similar exercises anymore.

The insights from the participants revealed that, consistent with previous research (e.g., Zou et al., 2023), ELSA Speak struggles with reduced accuracy under less-than-ideal conditions, such as noise, and occasionally fails to accurately recognise pronunciation despite multiple attempts. Notably, these results demonstrate that participants abandoned practice sessions due to frustration.

Content-related challenges

Although only two of seven participants highlighted challenges with the ELSA Speak application's capacity to effectively engage with the content of their conversations, their observations are worth exploring due to their potential impact on user experience, given the app's limitations. For instance, while Participant 6 expressed a desire to engage in in-depth discussions about computers, ELSA AI fell short of their expectations, struggling to handle technical or specialised topics:

I tried to explain, but ELSA didn't understand. The way ELSA AI did is to avoid and divert into another topic instead. It's quite limited if we go deeper into technical knowledge. Another thing is that that when I need to practice negotiating for a work contract, ELSA would probably give up. It can only talk about common knowledge.

This constraint may be attributed, as Amaral and Meurers (2011) concluded, to the lack of contributions from language educators during the development phase of an application or system. Consequently, to ensure learners sustain their ongoing intention to utilise the ELSA Speak application, it is important that these shortcomings be addressed and mitigated.

DISCUSSION

Over the course of a four-week study, data collected through observations, screen recordings, daily journal entries, and interviews with participants revealed that students do not passively use language learning applications. Rather, they deliberately and actively select features that meet their needs—in this case, the development of oral fluency. The ELSA Speak features that learners found particularly useful were those that offered them autonomy or flexibility to make choices, addressed their personal fluency goals, and provided meaningful, detailed feedback that extended beyond the pronunciation accuracy of individual words. For example, among many features, ‘Study by Topic’ was valued not only for vocabulary input but also for allowing flexible topic choice, while ‘ELSA AI Conversation’ supported spontaneous thinking and fluency-building through context-based conversations and the assessment of fluency performance.

The above insight highlights that, firstly, in an AI-mediated learning environment, affective factors such as feeling confident and in control remain crucial to sustaining learner engagement. This aligns with the arguments of Little (2004) and Ushioda (2011) that a sense of control and empowerment in one’s own learning processes is likely to intrinsically motivate learners to persist in their learning. Secondly, the finding supports Tavakoli et al. (2020) and Jung Youn (2023), who underscored the importance of authentic tasks in developing learners’ spoken proficiency and Xie et al. (2019) and Chiu et al. (2024), who demonstrated that multidimensional and adaptive personalised feedback promotes greater learner engagement and outcomes.

The study also found that participants benefited from strategically combining various ELSA Speak features in a coordinated manner. For instance, they were observed regularly using Practice Daily Lessons to support the improvements targeted by ‘Improve Pronunciation’. On the one hand, this suggests that learners perceive fluency as intertwined with or interdependent on pronunciation (Khau & Huynh, 2022). On the other hand, feature integration has frequently been observed in language learning applications and has been shown to support multiple dimensions of linguistic proficiency rather than focusing on a single aspect. Such integration has been shown to lower anxiety, promote learners’ engagement and increase their willingness to communicate (Hatmanto & Sari, 2023; Zhao et al., 2024).

The findings from the current study indicate that Vietnamese EFL university students generally hold positive perceptions toward ELSA Speak as a tool for improving English fluency, particularly due to its ability to enhance confidence, provide structured learning, offer consistent practice opportunities, and deliver detailed feedback — areas often found lacking in Vietnamese classroom settings (Tran & Tanemura, 2020).

Wang et al. (2024) found that learners who felt more engaged with AI tools and viewed them positively experienced greater learning enjoyment and achieved better outcomes. Additionally, Shafiee Rad (2024) and Mei et al. (2024) found a positive relationship between AI-supported tools and affective variables, such as confidence and motivation. The current study supports these findings in several ways. Firstly, differing attitudes between Participant 6 (more positive) and Participant 5 (less positive) appeared to influence the quality of their experiences with the app, reinforcing the role of affective engagement in learning outcomes. Secondly, participants reported increased self-efficacy and reduced nervousness in their real-life interactions, suggesting that ELSA Speak's impact extends beyond controlled practice and affects users' real-life communication skills.

Research has highlighted the capacity of AI-powered language tools to deliver scaffolded learning experiences, in which their content is organised to support learners' gradual skill development (Hatmanto & Sari, 2023). Findings showed that ELSA Speak reflects this principle through its diverse lessons and topics, presented systematically and in a structured way. Along with more detailed and comprehensive feedback, especially compared to that in traditional classrooms, participants reported benefiting from knowing their strengths and weaknesses, and consequently improving by following personalised practice suggestions that met their needs (Ebadi & Ebadijalal, 2022).

Despite its strengths, ELSA Speak has its limitations. A notable drawback is that it may not be suitable for long-term learning because it lacks a learning history feature. Reported by six participants, this limitation prevented them from revisiting past lessons or reinforcing specific skills, which may ultimately hinder the effectiveness of spaced repetition and long-term retention. This concern is relevant because it has not been adequately addressed in short-term studies (e.g., Bashori et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2023), which may thereby underestimate the challenges related to long-term engagement (van den Berghe et al., 2019).

Aligned with earlier criticisms of AI-based learning tools such as Zou et al. (2023) and Jeon (2022), participants in the current study also raised issues with ELSA Speak's technical performance, such as slow loading times, confusing interface, lack of specialised knowledge and most importantly, inconsistent recognition, which led to their frustration and abandonment of practice sessions. These issues are especially critical for users in under-resourced or noisy environments.

Notably, the notion that loud speech, rather than accuracy, could trick the system into awarding a high score (highlighted in the "Disadvantages of ELSA Speak" section) raises ethical and pedagogical questions about the reliability of AI feedback. The current study, therefore, aligns with previous research that the integration of AI-powered tools in language education must be pedagogically grounded and critically mediated, rather than implemented uncritically or in isolation (Yoshida, 2018).

Contributions of the current study

The current study has contributed to theoretical, methodological, and practical discussions in the field of Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) in TESOL, particularly in the context of AI-Assisted Language Learning (AILL).

Theoretical contributions

At the theoretical level, the current study makes several contributions to understanding MALL. Firstly, it affirms the usefulness of features that promote learner autonomy, authentic communication and comprehensive feedback for fluency development. Secondly, rather than viewing fluency as limited to speech rate or the number of pauses, as conceptualised by Arevart and Nation (1991) and Schmidt (1992), the current study highlights how learners perceived it to relate to motivation, confidence, and their strategic use of technological resources. This perspective adds depth to fluency research by emphasising the roles of affective (Dörnyei & Ryan, 2015) and metacognitive factors (Qiao & Zhao, 2023) in shaping learners' engagement with AI-driven language tools for fluency improvement.

Thirdly, the study sheds light on the challenges associated with the relatively long-term usability of ELSA Speak, raising concerns about novelty effects in prior research and suggesting the need for longitudinal studies to observe lasting effects (van den Berghe et al., 2019). Finally, it adds valuable cultural and contextual insight to the MALL literature by focusing on a Vietnamese university context—a relatively underrepresented population in MALL research (Ngoc & Dung, 2020). By

doing so, it expands the geographic and cultural scope of existing research, offering diverse perspectives on how learners from Southeast Asia interact with educational technologies in resource-constrained yet digitally connected environments.

Methodological contributions

The current study makes methodological contributions to MALL research in several ways. It demonstrates the value of employing a qualitative design that combines several data collection tools such as screen recordings, reflective journals, and semi-structured interviews. This approach enabled the capture of a rich understanding of how Vietnamese EFL university students engaged with the ELSA Speak app over an extended period. For example, while screen recordings revealed patterns of feature use and navigation behaviour, journal entries documented participants' daily reflections on progress, challenges, and motivations. According to Sántha and Malomsoki-Sántha (2023), this triangulation of data sources offered a more holistic view of the observed phenomenon than single-method studies.

Furthermore, the instruments developed for the current study, especially the journal prompts and interview questions, could elicit detailed perceptions of app features, usage strategies, motivation, progress, advantages, and disadvantages, among others. Researchers interested in exploring learners' interactions with mobile technologies may find the approach and instruments employed herein replicable and adaptable to other contexts or populations, especially when in-depth insights into learners' experiences are needed. Future researchers may also adapt the study's themes and findings to design questionnaires for quantitative or mixed methods studies, especially those aiming to quantify learners' preferences or engagement patterns in AILL contexts. In this way, the study contributes to the early stages of instrument development, thereby supporting the expansion of MALL research.

Notably, the study offers insights into managing participant engagement in future research. One challenge during the data collection phase was maintaining learner participation over a four-week period. In the first week, participants engaged enthusiastically, but from the second week onward, they began skipping practice sessions occasionally. Following the strategies suggested by Killien and Newton (1990) to address this, the researcher established a strong connection with participants from the start, showed appreciation for their time, and explained how

their involvement would contribute to the study's goals. Additionally, the participants were clearly informed about the study's duration, time commitment, and what participation entails, to mentally prepare and set realistic expectations before giving consent to participate. As such, with clear instructions, regular check-ins and gentle weekly or daily reminders, their engagement was quickly reestablished.

Finally, the study contributes to ongoing discussions about methodological trustworthiness in qualitative research (Holliday, 2015). By systematically aligning data sources and cross-verifying findings across different modes, the current study substantiates how triangulation can enhance the credibility of learner-centred research.

Pedagogical contributions

The findings of the current study offer several implications for English language educators. Specifically, the results highlight the potential for integrating ELSA Speak into classroom instruction by integrating specific ELSA Speak features into in-class learning objectives. For example, the 'Study by Topic' feature could be aligned with weekly speaking themes such as travel, technology, or relationships. Teachers could assign these topics for pre-class preparation and then apply the vocabulary and expressions practised through the app in in-class discussions, roleplays, or debates. This helps to address the challenge of limited in-class practice time often encountered in traditional crowded classroom environments.

As shown in the current study, participants often combined several features in a single use; for example, 'Daily Practice Lessons' with 'Improve Pronunciation'. However, some students may require initial guidance with navigating different features, interpreting app feedback or creating a study plan based on individual fluency goals. Educators could, for instance, conduct training workshops at the beginning of the term to guide students in using ELSA Speak more effectively. This helps to avoid frustration or disengagement due to misunderstandings about how the app functions, consistent with Hoi and Mu (2021).

To mitigate app limitations raised by participants, educators can play a mediating role by shifting their mindset, helping them move away from viewing ELSA Speak as a scoring system and instead embracing it as a resource for learning. In this case, learners reported that reading loudly could occasionally mislead the app into assigning higher pronunciation scores. Teachers could encourage them to treat ELSA Speak as a feedback tool and prompt them to pay close attention to, for

instance, the example audio, analyse it carefully, think about how their own pronunciation or speech compares to it, and focus on real progress rather than just marks. This can then be reinforced through peer-review activities, where students listen to each other's recordings and discuss pronunciation, stress, and fluency issues.

Finally, the reflective practices used in the current study—particularly the guided journal prompts—can be adapted for classroom use. Teachers may encourage students to keep a short learning journal (either digitally or in print) in which they reflect on the app features they used, why they chose them, and what they learned, thereby fostering learners' critical thinking and metacognitive awareness (Kessler, 2023). These reflections can then be discussed weekly in small groups or submitted for formative feedback, promoting learner autonomy and self-regulation (Qiao & Zhao, 2023).

Limitations and future research

While the current study offers valuable insights into learner engagement with ELSA Speak, several limitations must be acknowledged. The first limitation concerns its size. With a small sample size ($n = 7$), the findings are not intended to be generalisable to the wider population of EFL learners. To address this, future research could involve larger, more diverse participant groups, spanning different regions and age ranges, to capture more comprehensive learner experiences and perceptions. Another limitation is the relatively short study duration (4 weeks), which may not be sufficient to observe long-term changes in learners' behaviour or the sustained impact of ELSA Speak. Future studies could adopt a longitudinal design to enable researchers to track changes in fluency development and app engagement over a longer period.

Additionally, the study focused on a specific context — Vietnamese EFL university students — which may limit the transferability of its findings to learners in other contexts. Further research should conduct similar studies in different regions to determine whether learners in other contexts perceive and use ELSA Speak in similar ways. Finally, further research might investigate the role of teachers in integrating ELSA Speak into blended learning environments. It would be valuable to examine how educators perceive the app, how they support learners' use of it, and what challenges they face in incorporating such tools into their curriculum. This could inform the development of technological designs better aligned with educational needs and real-world learning and teaching contexts.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The present study has empirically substantiated the growing body of research on AILL by providing an in-depth exploration of Vietnamese EFL university students' perceptions and experiences with the ELSA Speak application. It has underscored the application's potential to develop oral fluency through authentic practice, personalised feedback and motivational design, among others, while also revealing key strengths and limitations based on learners' firsthand engagement with the tool. In many ways, ELSA Speak functions like a language trainer that never sleeps, always available to offer feedback, repetition, and encouragement. However, as with any trainer, learners' success hinges on multiple factors, most notably their motivation and persistence. To borrow an analogy, AI-mediated apps are like GPS systems, since they can guide, suggest, and reroute, but the learner must be the one who drives. Over-dependence on GPS can lead to a loss of critical thinking about direction.

In the age where AI is increasingly involved in education, the current study serves as a timely reminder: technology can support, but not replace, the human aspects of language learning. While ELSA Speak can scaffold fluency, the findings revealed several significant limitations, reinforcing the perspective that it cannot fully substitute the role of human teachers in language instruction. Looking ahead, as AI technologies continue to advance rapidly, so must our frameworks for understanding and integrating them into practice. Learners, particularly those who are younger or less experienced, will need the right support and guidance. Ultimately, the idea is not simply to use an AI application, but to do so in ways that empower learners and preserve their original and critical thinking.

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